

CERTIFICATE OF APPRECIATION

THIS CERTIFIES THAT
TAFAKKUR MANZILI
JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Gulamova Bibi Mukhlisa Makhmudjon kizi

EXPRESSION OF THE CONCEPT OF “SIN” IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

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